

Challenges and Countermeasures of Water Resources in Dili, Timor-Leste

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Abstract

Dili, Timor-Leste, faces significant challenges related to water resources, primarily due to rapid urbanization, growing population, and outdated infrastructure. Groundwater, constituting over 75% of the water supply, presents sustainability issues, while surface water resources contribute minimally, highlighting a critical need for effective water management. The study identifies several key issues affecting water resources in Dili. There is a heavy reliance on groundwater, which poses sustainability risks. The contribution of surface water is low, leading to vulnerabilities in the overall water supply system. Groundwater, which supplies over 75% of the city's water, is generally microbiologically safe, but several boreholes show elevated levels of minerals such as TDS and hardness. In contrast, surface water sources are more susceptible to biological and chemical contamination, with some locations recording high Water Quality Index (WQI) values and the presence of *E. coli* and Total Coliforms. This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the current state of water resources in Dili. The findings highlight the urgent need to enhance infrastructure, improve groundwater management, and diversify water sources. Implementing water-saving measures, expanding surface water utilization, and strengthening monitoring systems will be critical. Additionally, addressing climate impacts and fostering community engagement in water governance can build a more resilient and sustainable water system in Dili. This research is significant as it contributes to sustainable water resource management, specifically aligning with Timor-Leste's Strategic Development Plan (SDP) 2011-2030 and Sustainable Development Goal 6.

Keywords: *water resources, water quality index, groundwater, surface water, climate change, community participation.*

Introduction

Rapid population growth and urban expansion in Dili, Timor-Leste escalate the demand for essential urban services, particularly a reliable supply of clean water. Unfortunately, infrastructure development has not kept pace with this rising demand (Food and Agriculture Organization, 2007). The city's piped water system remains outdated and limited in coverage, with weak institutional coordination. As a result, water scarcity has become one of the most critical urban challenges in Dili, affecting households, industrial operations, and agricultural activities in surrounding areas.

Furthermore, Dili's water supply system is constrained by a lack of key infrastructure, such as dams, which are necessary for effective water storage and distribution. Without sufficient storage facilities, the city cannot capture excess water during the rainy season, leaving it vulnerable to water shortages during

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the dry season (ADB, 2022). The Comoro River Basin, which provides both surface water and groundwater, is unable to meet the growing demands of the city's population and industries, exacerbating the problem (A. M. Takeleb et al., 2018).

The increasing population and expanding economic activities are putting additional pressure on the city's already strained water management systems, which remain inadequate to meet the rising demand (A. M. Takeleb et al., 2018). As a result, water shortages are particularly pronounced during the dry season, and inefficient water management practices further contribute to scarcity.

Beyond quantity issues, water quality is also a major concern due to its direct impact on public health. Many communities, particularly those in peri-urban and informal settlements, rely on shallow wells or unprotected groundwater sources that are highly vulnerable to contamination (Pinto & Shrestha, 2016). During the dry season, these sources often dry up or produce unsafe water with elevated chemical and biological content. Consequently, residents are forced to store water or purchase it from private vendors an option that is costly and not always safe. The absence of adequate sanitation and sewage systems further exacerbates contamination risks, contributing to waterborne diseases such as diarrhea and typhoid fever (Allan H. Smith, 2000).

Recognizing the importance of water for national development, the Government of Timor-Leste has launched several initiatives through the National Water Resources Policy and the Strategic Development Plan (SDP) 2011-2030, aligned with SDG 6. The SDP targets universal access to safe, reliable, and sustainable drinking water by 2030 (Courvisanos & Boavida, 2017; Takeleb et al., 2020). Efforts include rehabilitation of old pipe networks, reduction of NRW, improvement of metering systems, and promotion of community-based water management to enhance local participation and accountability. The National Directorate of Water and Sanitation (NDWS) plays a central role in policy implementation, although it continues to face challenges in funding, technical capacity, and inter-agency coordination (A. Takeleb et al., 2018).

However, the gap between policy and actual implementation remains wide. A World Bank report (2014) indicates that nearly 60% of Timor-Leste's population still lacks access to safe drinking water (ADB, 2022). Even in urban areas like Dili, connection to the piped network does not guarantee consistent service, and many households receive water only for a few hours per day. Moreover, water allocation across sectors including domestic, industrial, and agricultural irrigation, remains unbalanced due to weak data systems and inadequate infrastructure (Giordano et al., 2019). This imbalance limits productivity and creates tensions between users in urban and rural areas.

Therefore, this study explored the challenges and countermeasures of water resources in Dili, Timor-Leste. First, the present status of both quantity and quality of water resources in Dili, Timor-Leste was investigated. Then, based on the local development requirements, the key challenges were disclosed. Finally, the countermeasures, such as infrastructure improvements, institutional strengthening and community engagement, were put forward to create a resilient water system.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted in Dili, the capital city of Timor-Leste, situated on the north coast of the island of Timor, stretching approximately 25 km east–west and 7–15 km north–south. Its flat terrain covers an area of around 53 km² and is bordered by steep mountainous ridges to the south (Takeleb et al., 2020). Based on the latest data, Dili has a population of 324,269, with an annual growth rate of 2.7 per cent (Statistics, 2023). Specifically, the research focused on four sub districts within the Comoro watershed

encompassing densely populated residential area, industrial zones, and pri urban settlements. Spatial analysis was carried out using maps that illustrate the water distribution network, locations of water treatment facilities, and settlement patterns to identify disparities in access to clean water across different zones. Geographically, Dili is situated along the northern coast of Timor Island.

Figure 1. a. Districts of Timor-Leste, b. Map Site Location c. Groundwater basin in Dili

The Comoro watershed covers an area of approximately 212 km² and serves as the primary water source for the city. Dili has a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons, and monthly rainfall between 2019 and 2024 ranged from 3.2 mm to 280.2 mm. Surface water is supplied by five major rivers—Bemos, Maloa, Nahaek, Lakoto, Mutudare, and Benamauk/Becora—which flow downstream and are utilized by water treatment facilities. Groundwater is recharged by aquifers influenced by the Comoro and Becora rivers (Takeleb et al., 2020) ADB, 2004; JICA, 2010). Currently, 25 active boreholes are distributed across four subdistricts and are managed by the National Directorate of Water and Sanitation (NDWS). These boreholes serve domestic, commercial, and industrial water needs and form a critical component of the city’s integrated urban water supply system.

Methodology

Water Quantity Analysis

The quantitative component of this study focuses on evaluating water availability, rainfall patterns, population density, and water consumption behavior. Data were collected through field surveys and

secondary sources, including government reports, census data, and hydrological records from the EDTL Hydrological Station. Descriptive statistics are used to summarize general trends, while Pearson correlation, linear regression, and cross-tabulation (chi-square test) are applied to examine relationships between variables such as rainfall, population density, and access to clean water. Although this study primarily focuses on a quantitative approach, the qualitative component, which includes limited interviews with representatives of the Water Authority and local communities provide important additional context.

Calculation of the Water Quality Index

The Water Quality Index (WQI) is used to assess the suitability of drinking water. This index is a flexible, unbiased, and time-efficient tool for evaluating the suitability of drinking water, assisting in prioritizing and maintaining water quality (Bouslah et al., 2017). WQI can be calculated using the weighted arithmetic index method, developed by Brown et al. (1972), through three main steps, IQW is calculated by selecting water quality parameters based on local regulations.

Step One: Calculate the unit weighting factor (W_n) for each parameter using Eqs. (1) and (2).

$$W_n = k/S_n \quad (1)$$

$$K = 1/(1/S_1 + 1/S_2 + 1/S_3 + \dots + 1/S_n) = 1/(\sum 1/S_n) \quad (2)$$

where S_n = the desired standard value of the n th parameter; the sum of all the unit weighting factors of the selected parameters must equal $W_n = 1$ (unit).

Step Two: Calculate the sub-index value (Q_n) using Eq. (3).

$$Q_n = ((V_n - V_o)) / ((S_n - V_o)) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

where V_n = the average concentration of the n th parameter; S_n = the desired standard value of the n th parameter; V_o = the actual value of the parameter in pure water (generally $V_o = 0$, except for pH). For pH, the formula is as shown in Eq. (4).

$$Q_{pH} = \frac{V_{pH}-7}{8.5-7} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Step Three: Combine Steps 1 and 2. WQI is calculated as Eq. (5).

$$WQI = \sum W_n Q_n / \sum W_n \quad (5)$$

As for the assessment of water quality, WQI has been classified into 5 classes. Table 1 represents the 5 classes of water quality based on WQI of arithmetic WQI method.

Table 1. WQI Range, Status and Possible Usage of the Water Sample

WQI range	Water quality status	Possible usage
0-25	Excellent Water Quality	Drinking, Irrigation and Industrial
26-50	Good Water Quality	Drinking, Irrigation and Industrial
51-75	Poor Water Quality	Irrigation and Industrial
76-100	Very Poor Water Quality	Irrigation
Above 100	Unsuitable for drinking and propagation of fish culture	Proper treatment required before use

Source: as Brown et al., 1972

Results and Discussion

Water Quantity

Supply and Demand of Water Resources

According to recent assessments, the quantity of water resources in Dili, Timor-Leste, based on operational data for September 2025, shows that the total actual water Available production reached 1192,819 cubic meters per month, which is 14,31 million m³/year. which summarizes the production volume from all active water sources in the study area.

This production of two main source categories: groundwater and surface water, as described in the Total Average Actual Water Production in Dili figure. Groundwater is obtained from more than twenty boreholes spread across the Comoro, Manleuana, Becora, Bidau, and Hera zones, with a total production of 902,347 cubic meters per month which is 75,65%, while the actual surface water is approximately 290,472 m³/month, which is 24,35%.

Based on these Total supplies, the heavy reliance on groundwater can lead to sustainability issues over time, particularly because groundwater reserves are generally limited and vulnerable to over-extraction. This risk becomes more pronounced in areas with low or inconsistent recharge rates. On the other hand, the contribution of surface water to the overall available is relatively low, thereby narrowing the range of alternative sources that can be relied upon in the long term (Takeleb et al., 2020).

According to the National Water and Sanitation Directorate, a water use in Dili is distributed across several categories which include Domestic, General, offices, social, and public tap. Water supply for general use is designated for commercial and industrial purposes, while social use is allocated to schools and religious places. The percentages for each category are as follows: domestic use accounts for 94.9%, general use 2.5%, offices 1.7%, social 0.4%, and public taps 0.3%, as shown in the figure 2a. This distribution, as shown in Figure 2a, clearly indicates that the largest share is allocated to domestic needs, suggesting that the main pressure on water use comes from household consumption. The highest concentrations are recorded in Dom Aleixo and Cristo Rei, areas characterized by high population density and intensive socio-economic activities (Cruz, 2016).

As illustrated in Figure 2b, total water use per subdistrict, Dom Aleixo contributes around 52.2% of the overall distribution, followed by Vera Cruz at 22.8%, while Nain Feto and Cristo Rei each account for 36.6%. The dominance of Dom Aleixo as the largest water user shows that this area represents the main pressure point in the city's water use system. Meanwhile, the lower proportions in Vera Cruz, Nain Feto, and Cristo Rei may reflect differences in demographic characteristics, population density, or levels of access to clean water services (Cruz, 2016).

Figure 2. a. Total Percent Water Use in Dili, East Timor
b. Total Percent Water Use in Sub-Districts

This overall distribution of water use indicates that water management strategies need to take into account the proportional burden of each area. High-consumption areas such as Dom Aleixo require more intensive approaches in terms of distribution efficiency, infrastructure strengthening, and diversification of water sources. Conversely, areas with lower consumption still need guaranteed accessibility and service quality to prevent inequality. Thus, a region-based approach is essential to ensure the resilience and sustainability of the urban water supply system.

While the total water Resources demand, stands at 1,167,368 m³ per month, this illustrates the current balance between supply and demand in Dili, This visual comparison confirms that the city is not currently experiencing an acute water shortage (Carrard et al., 2019).

Major Challenges of Water Quantity

While the data do not suggest an immediate crisis, the figure also highlights a critical dependency on groundwater, which accounts for over 75% of total production. This reliance poses long-term sustainability risks, particularly in areas with low or inconsistent recharge rates (Katusiime & Schütt, 2020). The relatively low contribution of surface water further emphasizes the vulnerability of the current supply structure. The major challenges of water quantity are listed as following.

(1) Heavy Reliance on Groundwater

Groundwater accounts for 75.65% of total water production (902,347 m³/month), sourced from over 20 boreholes across Comoro, Manleuana, Becora, Bidau, and Hera. The impact include risk of declining groundwater levels due to over-extraction; imbalance between extraction and recharge, especially in areas with low or inconsistent rainfall; and long-term reduction in production capacity and potential resource conflicts.

(2) Low Contribution from Surface Water

Surface water contributes only 24.35% (290,472 m³/month), despite the presence of rivers like Comoro and Maloa. The impacts include dependence on a single source (groundwater) reduces system flexibility; high rainfall events (up to 696.55 mm/month) can cause flooding, damaging infrastructure and contaminating water sources; and missed opportunity to capture and treat rainwater during wet seasons.

(3) Narrow Margin Between Supply and Demand

Total water production: 1,192,819 m³/month. Total water demand: 1,167,368 m³/month. The impacts include that the system is highly vulnerable to small disruptions such as demand spikes, technical failures, or climate variability; and lack of operational reserves to respond to emergencies or population growth.

(4) Uneven Distribution of Water Connections

Out of 13,604 active connections, 95% are for domestic use, with high concentrations in Dom Aleixo (6,747 connections) and Cristo Rei (2,781 connections). The impacts include localized pressure on distribution networks, risking service disruptions; and limited access to clean water in social and public sectors, which have only 41 public tap connections.

(5) Inconsistent Groundwater Quality

Groundwater WQI values range from Excellent (Becora 2: 1.17) to Very Poor (Tuanalaran: 72.76). The impacts include reduced volume of usable water due to poor quality in several boreholes; increased need for water treatment, raising operational costs and reducing supply efficiency; and public health risks if untreated water is used for domestic purposes. Thus, although the supply slightly exceeds demand at present, the balance remains fragile and could shift rapidly due to changes in groundwater levels, rising consumption, or environmental pressures. Careful and adaptive water resource management is essential to maintain this equilibrium and ensure long-term resilience.

Water Quality

Surface water quality

The evaluation of water resource quality in Dili was conducted through laboratory analysis of 25 groundwater points and 5 surface water points. The water supply must be determined according to whether water samples are suitable for human consumption, considering certain physical, chemical, and biological characteristics (da Costa et al., 2024). In this study, in order to calculate WQI, we chose several parameters based on the national drinking water quality standard in Timor-Leste. The standard also refers to WHO guidelines ((WHO)), according to the ministry of health in Timor-Leste (da Costa et al., 2024). Microbiology parameters were fully selected because some research studies have shown that those parameters are crucial to estimate the contamination of the water (Wada et al., 2014). Consequently, we focused on 10 water quality parameters to compute WQI.

The presents data on the water quality of surface water from various locations in Dili, Timor-Leste, based on a set of parameters such as pH, TDS (Total Dissolved Solids), turbidity, hardness, NO₃-N (Nitrate Nitrogen), Iron, Manganese, Sulphate, T.Coli, and E.Coli. These parameters are used to assess the overall quality Index of the surface water at different sites (da Costa et al., 2024).

Table 2. Analytical Data Surface Water of Dili, Timor-Leste

Parameters	Standard Sn	Bee Mos Comoro	Maloa	Nahaek	Mutudare	BeeMauk
pH	6.5 - 8.5	8.41	8.34	7.56	7.79	7.95
TDS	1000	123.6	148	191.3	121.7	140.2
Turbidity	5	0.26	0.61	0.14	0.3	0.587
Hardness	110-500	100	150	68	66	96
NO ₃ -N	11	0.27	0.19	2.27	0.7	0.36
Iron	0.3	0.15	0.02	0.1	0.05	0.05
Manganese	0.05	0.011	0.011	0.04	0.004	0.01
Sulphate	250	10.67	6	16	11	9
T.Coli	0	0	7	0	0	0
E.Coli	0	0	5	0	0	0

Sources: BTL, Ep, DNCQA

Based on the WQI values for different locations provided earlier: Mutudare, and Bemauk are in the excellent water quality range, making them safe and suitable for all uses. These findings indicate potential biological contamination, requiring increased catchment protection and strengthening of water treatment systems (Vanham et al., 2018). Bee Mos Comoro falls in the Good water quality range, still safe but with some minor contamination. Nahaek/Lahane and Maloa are in the Very poor water quality range, meaning the water is not safe for drinking and requires urgent attention and treatment, but Maloa—which recorded the presence of *E. coli* (5 N/100 mL) and Total Coliforms (7 N/100 mL) (Maldonado-Devis & Castellet-Viciano, 2019; Talpur et al., 2024).

Figure 3. WQI and Status of Water Quality of Surface Water in Dili, Timor-Leste

Table Calculation WQI Result presents the SurfaceWQI values for five different locations: Mutudare, Bemauk, Bee Mos Comoro, Maloa, and Nahaek/Lahane. The WQI is used to assess the overall condition of water quality based on physical, chemical, and biological parameters. A lower WQI value indicates better water quality (Chidiac et al., 2023).

Mutudare and Bemauk recorded WQI values of 9.5 and 19.55 respectively, both falling under the Excellent water quality category (Chidiac et al., 2023). This suggests that the water in these locations is safe for various uses, including direct consumption. Bee Mos Comoro, with a WQI value of 29.98, is classified as *Good*. The water remains suitable for use, although minor contamination is present and should be monitored regularly (Chaturvedi & Bassin, 2010).

In contrast, Maloa and Nahaek/Lahane show significantly higher WQI values of 68.65 and 72.62, respectively, placing them in the *Very Poor* category. According to the water quality table from BROWN et al. (1972), this indicates that the water in these areas is unsafe for drinking and suitable only for irrigation, requiring urgent treatment and remediation. Such conditions may reflect contamination from domestic activities, unmanaged waste, or inadequate sanitation infrastructure (Flörke et al., 2018).

Overall, the chart provides a comparative overview of surface water quality across the five locations and highlights areas that require greater environmental attention and policy intervention to improve water safety and sustainability.

Groundwater quality

The presented analytical data on the groundwater quality from various locations in Dili, Timor-Leste. The table below provides the detailed measurements for each borehole and standard, offering a comprehensive overview of the groundwater quality at the various sampling points.

Figure 4. WQI and Status of Water Quality of Ground Water in Dili, Timor-Leste

The groundwater WQI chart provides a comprehensive overview of groundwater quality conditions across various borehole locations in Dili. WQI values range from 1.17 to 72.76, indicating a wide variation in water quality between sites. According to water quality classification table lower WQI values (0-25) reflect better groundwater quality, while higher values suggest potential contamination and increased health risks (Bouslah et al., 2017). Several locations, such as Becora 2 (1.17), Camea Maloa (3.74), and Culuhun B (3.93), exhibit excellent groundwater quality. Water from these boreholes is likely safe for domestic use, including drinking, with minimal contamination risk. These sites are likely situated in areas with low environmental pressure and stable geological conditions (Muller, 2018).

However, the chart also reveals boreholes with high WQI values, including Tuanalaran (72.76), Jardim 5 de Maio (69.93), and Bidau 1 (65.39). These fall into the Poor category, indicating that the groundwater is unsuitable for consumption without prior treatment. Such conditions may reflect contamination from domestic waste, agricultural runoff, or inadequate sanitation infrastructure in surrounding areas. Most other boreholes fall within the moderate range, such as Comoro C (50.92) and Mota Ulun (49.40), categorized as *Poor to Marginal*. Water from these locations may still be usable for limited purposes but requires regular monitoring and technical treatment to ensure safety (Hussain et al., 2024).

Overall, the chart demonstrates that groundwater quality in Dili is not uniform and is heavily influenced by local factors such as land use, population density, and environmental conditions (Wada et al., 2010). This underscores the need for a more integrated and sustainable groundwater monitoring system to detect changes early and guide appropriate interventions. Locations with poor water quality should be prioritized for investigation and remediation, while areas with good quality must be protected from future degradation (Liu et al., 2017). The chart serves not only as a technical evaluation tool but also as a foundation for water policy planning, environmental protection, and public education on the importance of safeguarding groundwater resources sustainably.

Major challenges of water quality

(1) Biological Contamination in Surface Water

Several locations, such as Maloa and Nahaek/Lahane, show the presence of *E. coli* and Total Coliforms, exceeding the acceptable limits for drinking water. The major impacts include is unsafe water for direct consumption without treatment; increased risk of waterborne diseases; and requires enhanced catchment protection and improved water treatment infrastructure.

(2) Inconsistent Groundwater Quality Across Boreholes

Groundwater WQI values range widely from 1.17 (Excellent) to 72.76 (Very Poor), indicating significant variation in water safety. The major impacts include several unsuitable borehole for domestic use without treatment; higher operational costs due to increased water treatment needs; and reduced efficiency in water supply systems and potential public health risks.

(3) Physical and Chemical Parameter Deviations

Some surface water samples show low hardness (66-100 mg/L) and low TDS, which may affect water stability and infrastructure. The major impacts include corrosion of pipes and distribution systems; potential issues with taste and mineral balance; and requires adjustment in treatment and distribution protocols.

(4) Environmental and Human Activity Impacts

Contamination in areas like Bidau and Jardim 5 de Maio may be linked to domestic waste, agricultural runoff, and poor sanitation infrastructure. The major impacts include localized degradation of water quality; health risks for communities near contaminated sources; and land use regulation and targeted environmental interventions.

(5) Lack of Integrated Monitoring System

The wide variation in water quality suggests that monitoring is not yet comprehensive or continuous. The major impacts include delayed detection of water quality deterioration; reactive rather than preventive responses to contamination; urgent need for a location-based, parameter-specific monitoring framework.

Countermeasures for the Challenges of Water Resources

Water resource management in Dili faces multidimensional and interrelated challenges, encompassing technical, environmental, and institutional aspects. The city relies heavily on groundwater, which accounts for more than 75% of total water production, while the contribution from surface water remains low despite the presence of five major rivers flowing through the region. This dependency is further complicated by inconsistent groundwater quality, with several boreholes showing high WQI values that render the water unsuitable for consumption without treatment (Tripathi et al., 2021). On the other hand, surface water sources also face serious challenges, particularly biological contamination such as *E. coli* and Total Coliforms, as recorded in locations like Maloa and Nahaek/Lahane.

One of the most urgent issues is the extremely high rate of water losses, which reaches 96%. This means that nearly all produced water fails to reach consumers due to leaks, illegal connections, and inaccurate metering systems, ultimately affecting the overall availability of water resources (McDonald et al., 2011). Based on the data, groundwater accounts for 75.65% of the total water production, or 902,347 m³ per month, highlighting the heavy dependence on this resource. However, groundwater is limited and vulnerable to over-extraction, especially in areas with low or inconsistent recharge rates. Additionally, surface water contributes only 24.35% of the total production, or 290,472 m³ per month, further restricting the options for water Available. This imbalance between groundwater and surface water

resources emphasizes the urgent need to address distribution inefficiencies and diversify water sources to ensure long-term water security and resilience. Despite the available water production being sufficient to meet demand, the system's vulnerability to disruptions makes it critical to manage water resources more efficiently and reduce dependence on a single resource.

In terms of water quality, laboratory analysis of 25 groundwater points and 5 surface water points reveals significant variation. Locations such as Mutudare and Bemauk show excellent water quality, while others like Tuanalaran and Jardim 5 de Maio record poor WQ values. This irregularity reflects the absence of a fully integrated water quality monitoring system (Grafton et al., 2023). Moreover, extreme rainfall fluctuations from as low as 8.17 mm to as high as 696.55 mm per month, add complexity to water distribution and storage planning, as the current system is not yet capable of responding adaptively to seasonal changes (Lim et al., 2023).

The following countermeasures are vital to enhance the resilience and sustainability of the urban water system.

(1) Reducing Water Losses

Given these conditions, the first strategic response should focus on reducing water losses, as it represents the most urgent and cost-effective intervention. This includes systematic leak detection by implementing technologies for constant monitoring to identify and repair leaks in the distribution network; pipe replacement to gradually phase out aging infrastructure, minimizing leakage and improving system reliability; and the implementation of IoT- and SCADA-based monitoring technologies, which can significantly improve distribution efficiency (Abidin et al., 2009).

(2) Improving Surface Water Utilization

Despite the existence of several rivers, the contribution of surface water is limited. Countermeasures include rehabilitation of treatment facilities which involves upgrade existing water treatment infrastructures to improve the quality of surface water for consumption; catchment protection, which should implement measures to protect water catchment areas from pollution and deforestation; and the application of simple treatment technologies such as modular filtration and UV disinfection, particularly in peri-urban areas (Smajgl et al., 2015).

(3) Strengthening Water Quality Monitoring

To ensure the safety and reliability of water resources in Dili, it is imperative to strengthen the water quality monitoring system through an integrated approach. This encompasses the development of a centralized water quality database, training local technicians in testing physical, chemical, and biological parameters, and using portable testing kits and digital dashboards for data visualization.

(4) Expanding Access to Water Services

To ensure equitable access to safe water, it is essential to focus on several key initiatives. Expanding the coverage of the piped water network will reach underserved communities; increasing the number of public taps should also be a medium-term priority; and using community-based planning and offering incentives for households to connect officially. This approach can offer incentives for households to formalize their water connections, fostering greater participation and accountability.

(5) Climate Adaptation Strategies

Long-term water resource planning must consider climate variability. This includes implementing seasonal storage solutions, such as retention ponds and underground storage tanks, to capture excess rainfall and provide water during dry periods; flood-resilient infrastructure should be constructed to withstand extreme weather events, thereby reducing vulnerability; (Aboelnga et al., 2019). and risk

mapping and early warning systems must be developed to predict and mitigate the impacts of extreme weather events, supporting emergency preparedness (Abusaada & Elshater, 2021).

(6) Institutional Strengthening and Community Engagement

Sustainable water management requires strong institutions and community support. This includes multi-stakeholder governance platforms, which establish platforms that engage government, NGOs, and local communities in water management discussions; public education campaigns to promote awareness about water conservation and hygiene practices through targeted campaigns; and community-based management committees, which empower local communities to participate in water governance and resource management.

In short, with an integrated and phased approach, Dili can build a more resilient, equitable, and sustainable urban water system aligned with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 6. These strategies not only address current deficiencies but also prepare the city to face future environmental and social pressures.

Conclusions

This study highlights the urgent challenges facing Dili's water resources, primarily stemming from heavy reliance on groundwater, insufficient surface water utilization, and significant quality discrepancies. The findings reveal that groundwater constitutes over 75% of the city's supply, but poses sustainability risks due to potential over-extraction and contamination. Notably, several boreholes demonstrate poor water quality, emphasizing public health concerns. The research underscores the critical need for integrated water resource management strategies, including the enhancement of infrastructure, diversification of water sources, and robust community engagement. By aligning local initiatives with national objectives, such as Timor-Leste's Strategic Development Plan, this study contributes to ongoing efforts towards sustainable water management, ensuring equitable access to safe water for the growing population in Dili.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declares no conflict of interest

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Appendix

Table 3. Analytical Data Groundwater in Dili, Timor-Leste

Parameters	Standard Sn	Comoro C	Comoro D	Comoro E	Comoro B1	Comoro B	Comoro A	Mercado Manleu	Manleu Aasgor	Bairo Pite A	Coperativa Office	Jardim 5 de Maio	Tuanalaran	My Friend	Mascarinhas	Culuhun A	Culuhun B	Becora Auhun	Becora 1 Cispol	Becora 2Maufelu	Camea Ailok laran	Camea Sede Suco	Camea Cendana	Bidau 2	Bbidau 3	Hera
pH	6.5 - 8.5	7,88	7,81	7,7	7,8	7,3	7,96	8	7,81	7,73	8,26	7,8	7,2	7,46	7,4	7,09	7,19	7,5	7,6	7,2	7,6	7,3	7	7,5	7,2	7,3
TDS	1000	249	183	182	171	165	162	145,2	170	368	849	428	216	190	477	254	317	209	230	304	233	249	251	230	232	214
Turbidity	5	0.13	0.21	0.2	0.23	0.24	0.15	0.19	0.22	0.17	1.01	0.21	0.36	0.16	0.2	0.19	0.31	0.17	0.27	0.15	0.79	0.24	0.27	0.17	0.197	0.14
Hardness	110-500	164	146	150	144	146	134	120	124	204	244	192	182	150	220	190	198	156	190	198	180	174	176	170	182	140
NO ₃ -N	11	1.62	1.06	0.9	0.52	0.54	0.58	0.01	0.79	3.89	1.38	2.01	1.95	2.09	4.12	4.61	5.55	3.54	3.91	6.65	3.49	4	4.01	3.7	3.56	1.17
Iron	0.3	0.18	0.18	0.14	0.16	0.02	0.16	0.14	0.01	0.03	0.06	0.2	0.29	0.02	0.1	0.27	0.03	0.07	0.15	0.1	0.01	0.12	0.06	0.02	0.3	0.03
Manganese	0.05	0.025	0.01	0.017	0.026	0.016	0.003	0	0.007	0.02	0.015	0.005	0.033	0.02	0.04	0	0.003	0	0	0.026	0	0	0	0.017	0.03	0.007
Sulphate	250	11	13	22	7	1	22	21	22	35	53	35	20	9	26	33	33	15	38	9	30	23	37	16	27	13
T.Coli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E.Coli	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sources: BTL, Ep, DNCQA

